

Switching Equivalence in Symmetric n -Sigraphs-V

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Abstract: An n -tuple (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) is *symmetric*, if $a_k = a_{n-k+1}, 1 \leq k \leq n$. Let $H_n = \{(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) : a_k \in \{+, -\}, a_k = a_{n-k+1}, 1 \leq k \leq n\}$ be the set of all symmetric n -tuples. A *symmetric n -sigraph* (*symmetric n -marked graph*) is an ordered pair $S_n = (G, \sigma)$ ($S_n = (G, \mu)$), where $G = (V, E)$ is a graph called the *underlying graph* of S_n and $\sigma : E \rightarrow H_n$ ($\mu : V \rightarrow H_n$) is a function. In this paper, we introduced a new notion \mathcal{S} -antipodal symmetric n -sigraph of a symmetric n -sigraph and its properties are obtained. Also we give the relation between antipodal symmetric n -sigraphs and \mathcal{S} -antipodal symmetric n -sigraphs. Further, we discuss structural characterization of \mathcal{S} -antipodal symmetric n -sigraphs.

Key Words: Symmetric n -sigraphs, Smarandachely symmetric n -marked graph, symmetric n -marked graphs, balance, switching, antipodal symmetric n -sigraphs, \mathcal{S} -antipodal symmetric n -sigraphs, complementation.

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§1. Introduction

Unless mentioned or defined otherwise, for all terminology and notion in graph theory the reader is refer to [1]. We consider only finite, simple graphs free from self-loops.

Let $n \geq 1$ be an integer. An n -tuple (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) is *symmetric*, if $a_k = a_{n-k+1}, 1 \leq k \leq n$. Let $H_n = \{(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) : a_k \in \{+, -\}, a_k = a_{n-k+1}, 1 \leq k \leq n\}$ be the set of all symmetric n -tuples. Note that H_n is a group under coordinate wise multiplication, and the order of H_n is 2^m , where $m = \lceil \frac{n}{2} \rceil$.

A *Smarandachely k -marked graph* (*Smarandachely k -signed graph*) is an ordered pair $S = (G, \mu)$ ($S = (G, \sigma)$) where $G = (V, E)$ is a graph called *underlying graph* of S and $\mu : V \rightarrow \{\bar{e}_1, \bar{e}_2, \dots, \bar{e}_k\}$ ($\sigma : E \rightarrow \{\bar{e}_1, \bar{e}_2, \dots, \bar{e}_k\}$) is a function, where $\bar{e}_i \in \{+, -\}$. An n -tuple (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) is *symmetric*, if $a_k = a_{n-k+1}, 1 \leq k \leq n$. Let $H_n = \{(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) : a_k \in \{+, -\}, a_k = a_{n-k+1}, 1 \leq k \leq n\}$ be the set of all symmetric n -tuples. A *Smarandachely symmetric n -marked graph* (*Smarandachely symmetric n -signed graph*) is an ordered pair $S_n = (G, \mu)$ ($S_n = (G, \sigma)$) where $G = (V, E)$ is a graph called the *underlying graph* of S_n and $\mu : V \rightarrow H_n$ ($\sigma : E \rightarrow H_n$) is a function. Particularly, a Smarandachely 1-marked graph (Smarandachely 1-signed graph) is called a *marked graph* (*signed graph*).

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In this paper by an n -tuple/ n -sigraph/ n -marked graph we always mean a symmetric n -tuple/symmetric n -sigraph/symmetric n -marked graph.

An n -tuple (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) is the *identity n -tuple*, if $a_k = +$, for $1 \leq k \leq n$, otherwise it is a *non-identity n -tuple*. In an n -sigraph $S_n = (G, \sigma)$ an edge labelled with the identity n -tuple is called an *identity edge*, otherwise it is a *non-identity edge*. Further, in an n -sigraph $S_n = (G, \sigma)$, for any $A \subseteq E(G)$ the n -tuple $\sigma(A)$ is the product of the n -tuples on the edges of A .

In [7], the authors defined two notions of balance in n -sigraph $S_n = (G, \sigma)$ as follows (See also R. Rangarajan and P.S.K.Reddy [4]):

Definition 1.1 Let $S_n = (G, \sigma)$ be an n -sigraph. Then,

- (i) S_n is identity balanced (or i -balanced), if product of n -tuples on each cycle of S_n is the identity n -tuple, and
- (ii) S_n is balanced, if every cycle in S_n contains an even number of non-identity edges.

Note 1.1 An i -balanced n -sigraph need not be balanced and conversely.

The following characterization of i -balanced n -sigraphs is obtained in [7].

Proposition 1.1 (E. Sampathkumar et al. [7]) An n -sigraph $S_n = (G, \sigma)$ is i -balanced if, and only if, it is possible to assign n -tuples to its vertices such that the n -tuple of each edge uv is equal to the product of the n -tuples of u and v .

Let $S_n = (G, \sigma)$ be an n -sigraph. Consider the n -marking μ on vertices of S_n defined as follows: each vertex $v \in V$, $\mu(v)$ is the n -tuple which is the product of the n -tuples on the edges incident with v . Complement of S_n is an n -sigraph $\overline{S_n} = (\overline{G}, \sigma^c)$, where for any edge $e = uv \in \overline{G}$, $\sigma^c(uv) = \mu(u)\mu(v)$. Clearly, $\overline{S_n}$ as defined here is an i -balanced n -sigraph due to Proposition 1.1 ([10]).

In [7], the authors also have defined switching and cycle isomorphism of an n -sigraph $S_n = (G, \sigma)$ as follows (See also [2,5,6,10]):

Let $S_n = (G, \sigma)$ and $S'_n = (G', \sigma')$, be two n -sigraphs. Then S_n and S'_n are said to be *isomorphic*, if there exists an isomorphism $\phi : G \rightarrow G'$ such that if uv is an edge in S_n with label (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) then $\phi(u)\phi(v)$ is an edge in S'_n with label (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) .

Given an n -marking μ of an n -sigraph $S_n = (G, \sigma)$, *switching* S_n with respect to μ is the operation of changing the n -tuple of every edge uv of S_n by $\mu(u)\sigma(uv)\mu(v)$. The n -sigraph obtained in this way is denoted by $\mathcal{S}_\mu(S_n)$ and is called the μ -switched n -sigraph or just *switched n -sigraph*. Further, an n -sigraph S_n switches to n -sigraph S'_n (or that they are *switching equivalent* to each other), written as $S_n \sim S'_n$, whenever there exists an n -marking of S_n such that $\mathcal{S}_\mu(S_n) \cong S'_n$.

Two n -sigraphs $S_n = (G, \sigma)$ and $S'_n = (G', \sigma')$ are said to be *cycle isomorphic*, if there exists an isomorphism $\phi : G \rightarrow G'$ such that the n -tuple $\sigma(C)$ of every cycle C in S_n equals to the n -tuple $\sigma(\phi(C))$ in S'_n . We make use of the following known result (see [7]).

Proposition 1.2 (E. Sampathkumar et al. [7]) Given a graph G , any two n -sigraphs with G

as underlying graph are switching equivalent if, and only if, they are cycle isomorphic.

Let $S_n = (G, \sigma)$ be an n -sigraph. Consider the n -marking μ on vertices of S defined as follows: each vertex $v \in V$, $\mu(v)$ is the product of the n -tuples on the edges incident at v . Complement of S is an n -sigraph $\overline{S}_n = (\overline{G}, \sigma')$, where for any edge $e = uv \in \overline{G}$, $\sigma'(uv) = \mu(u)\mu(v)$. Clearly, \overline{S}_n as defined here is an i -balanced n -sigraph due to Proposition 1.1.

§2. \mathcal{S} -Antipodal n -Sigraphs

Radhakrishnan Nair and Vijayakumar [3] has introduced the concept of \mathcal{S} -antipodal graph of a graph G as the graph $A^*(G)$ has the vertices in G with maximum eccentricity and two vertices of $A^*(G)$ are adjacent if they are at a distance of $diam(G)$ in G .

Motivated by the existing definition of complement of an n -sigraph, we extend the notion of \mathcal{S} -antipodal graphs to n -sigraphs as follows:

The \mathcal{S} -antipodal n -sigraph $A^*(S_n)$ of an n -sigraph $S_n = (G, \sigma)$ is an n -sigraph whose underlying graph is $A^*(G)$ and the n -tuple of any edge uv is $A^*(S_n)$ is $\mu(u)\mu(v)$, where μ is the canonical n -marking of S_n . Further, an n -sigraph $S_n = (G, \sigma)$ is called \mathcal{S} -antipodal n -sigraph, if $S_n \cong A^*(S'_n)$ for some n -sigraph S'_n . The following result indicates the limitations of the notion $A^*(S_n)$ as introduced above, since the entire class of i -unbalanced n -sigraphs is forbidden to be \mathcal{S} -antipodal n -sigraphs.

Proposition 2.1 For any n -sigraph $S_n = (G, \sigma)$, its \mathcal{S} -antipodal n -sigraph $A^*(S_n)$ is i -balanced.

Proof Since the n -tuple of any edge uv in $A^*(S_n)$ is $\mu(u)\mu(v)$, where μ is the canonical n -marking of S_n , by Proposition 1.1, $A^*(S_n)$ is i -balanced. \square

For any positive integer k , the k^{th} iterated \mathcal{S} -antipodal n -sigraph $A^*(S_n)$ of S_n is defined as follows:

$$(A^*)^0(S_n) = S_n, (A^*)^k(S_n) = A^*((A^*)^{k-1}(S_n))$$

Corollary 2.2 For any n -sigraph $S_n = (G, \sigma)$ and any positive integer k , $(A^*)^k(S_n)$ is i -balanced.

In [3], the authors characterized those graphs that are isomorphic to their \mathcal{S} -antipodal graphs.

Proposition 2.3(Radhakrishnan Nair and Vijayakumar [3]) For a graph $G = (V, E)$, $G \cong A^*(G)$ if, and only if, G is a regular self-complementary graph.

We now characterize the n -sigraphs that are switching equivalent to their \mathcal{S} -antipodal n -sigraphs.

Proposition 2.4 For any n -sigraph $S_n = (G, \sigma)$, $S_n \sim A^*(S_n)$ if, and only if, G is regular

self-complementary graph and S_n is i -balanced n -sigraph.

Proof Suppose $S_n \sim A^*(S_n)$. This implies, $G \cong A^*(G)$ and hence G is a regular self-complementary graph. Now, if S_n is any n -sigraph with underlying graph as regular self-complementary graph, Proposition 2.1 implies that $A^*(S_n)$ is i -balanced and hence if S is i -unbalanced and its $A^*(S_n)$ being i -balanced can not be switching equivalent to S_n in accordance with Proposition 1.2. Therefore, S_n must be i -balanced.

Conversely, suppose that S_n is an i -balanced n -sigraph and G is regular self-complementary. Then, since $A^*(S_n)$ is i -balanced as per Proposition 2.1 and since $G \cong A^*(G)$, the result follows from Proposition 1.2 again. \square

Proposition 2.5 *For any two vs S_n and S'_n with the same underlying graph, their \mathcal{S} -antipodal n -sigraphs are switching equivalent.*

Remark 2.6 If G is regular self-complementary graph, then $G \cong \overline{G}$. The above result is holds good for $\overline{S_n} \sim A^*(S_n)$.

In [16], P.S.K.Reddy et al. introduced antipodal n -sigraph of an n -sigraph as follows:

The *antipodal n -sigraph* $A(S_n)$ of an n -sigraph $S_n = (G, \sigma)$ is an n -sigraph whose underlying graph is $A(G)$ and the n -tuple of any edge uv in $A(S_n)$ is $\mu(u)\mu(v)$, where μ is the canonical n -marking of S_n . Further, an n -sigraph $S_n = (G, \sigma)$ is called antipodal n -sigraph, if $S_n \cong A(S'_n)$ for some n -sigraph S'_n .

Proposition 2.7(P.S.K.Reddy et al. [16]) *For any n -sigraph $S_n = (G, \sigma)$, its antipodal n -sigraph $A(S_n)$ is i -balanced.*

We now characterize n -sigraphs whose \mathcal{S} -antipodal n -sigraphs and antipodal n -sigraphs are switching equivalent. In case of graphs the following result is due to Radhakrishnan Nair and Vijayakumar [3].

Proposition 2.8 *For a graph $G = (V, E)$, $A^*(G) \cong A(G)$ if, and only if, G is self-centred.*

Proposition 2.9 *For any n -sigraph $S_n = (G, \sigma)$, $A^*(S_n) \sim A(S_n)$ if, and only if, G is self-centred.*

Proof Suppose $A^*(S_n) \sim A(S_n)$. This implies, $A^*(G) \cong A(G)$ and hence by Proposition 2.8, we see that the graph G must be self-centred.

Conversely, suppose that G is self centred. Then $A^*(G) \cong A(G)$ by Proposition 2.8. Now, if S_n is an n -sigraph with underlying graph as self centred, by Propositions 2.1 and 2.7, $A^*(S_n)$ and $A(S_n)$ are i -balanced and hence, the result follows from Proposition 1.2.

In [3], the authors shown that $A^*(G) \cong A^*(\overline{G})$ if G is either complete or totally disconnected. We now characterize n -sigraphs whose $A^*(S_n)$ and $A^*(\overline{S_n})$ are switching equivalent.

Proposition 2.10 *For any signed graph $S = (G, \sigma)$, $A^*(S_n) \sim A^*(\overline{S_n})$ if, and only if, G is either complete or totally disconnected.*

The following result characterize n -sigraphs which are \mathcal{S} -antipodal n -sigraphs.

Proposition 2.11 *An n -sigraph $S_n = (G, \sigma)$ is a \mathcal{S} -antipodal n -sigraph if, and only if, S_n is i -balanced n -sigraph and its underlying graph G is a \mathcal{S} -antipodal graph.*

Proof Suppose that S_n is i -balanced and G is a $A(G)$. Then there exists a graph H such that $A^*(H) \cong G$. Since S_n is i -balanced, by Proposition 1.1, there exists an n -marking μ of G such that each edge uv in S_n satisfies $\sigma(uv) = \mu(u)\mu(v)$. Now consider the n -sigraph $S'_n = (H, \sigma')$, where for any edge e in H , $\sigma'(e)$ is the n -marking of the corresponding vertex in G . Then clearly, $A^*(S'_n) \cong S_n$. Hence S_n is a \mathcal{S} -antipodal n -sigraph.

Conversely, suppose that $S_n = (G, \sigma)$ is a \mathcal{S} -antipodal n -sigraph. Then there exists an n -sigraph $S'_n = (H, \sigma')$ such that $A^*(S'_n) \cong S_n$. Hence G is the $A^*(G)$ of H and by Proposition 2.1, S_n is i -balanced. \square

§3. Complementation

In this section, we investigate the notion of complementation of a graph whose edges have signs (a *sigraph*) in the more general context of graphs with multiple signs on their edges. We look at two kinds of complementation: complementing some or all of the signs, and reversing the order of the signs on each edge.

For any $m \in H_n$, the m -complement of $a = (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n)$ is: $a^m = am$. For any $M \subseteq H_n$, and $m \in H_n$, the m -complement of M is $M^m = \{a^m : a \in M\}$. For any $m \in H_n$, the m -complement of an n -sigraph $S_n = (G, \sigma)$, written (S_n^m) , is the same graph but with each edge label $a = (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n)$ replaced by a^m . For an n -sigraph $S_n = (G, \sigma)$, the $A^*(S_n)$ is i -balanced (Proposition 2.1). We now examine, the condition under which m -complement of $A(S_n)$ is i -balanced, where for any $m \in H_n$.

Proposition 3.1 *Let $S_n = (G, \sigma)$ be an n -sigraph. Then, for any $m \in H_n$, if $A^*(G)$ is bipartite then $(A^*(S_n))^m$ is i -balanced.*

Proof Since, by Proposition 2.1, $A^*(S_n)$ is i -balanced, for each k , $1 \leq k \leq n$, the number of n -tuples on any cycle C in $A^*(S_n)$ whose k^{th} co-ordinate are $-$ is even. Also, since $A^*(G)$ is bipartite, all cycles have even length; thus, for each k , $1 \leq k \leq n$, the number of n -tuples on any cycle C in $A^*(S_n)$ whose k^{th} co-ordinate are $+$ is also even. This implies that the same thing is true in any m -complement, where for any $m, \in H_n$. Hence $(A^*(S_n))^t$ is i -balanced. \square

Problem 3.2 *Characterize these n -sigraphs for which*

- (1) $(S_n)^m \sim A^*(S_n)$;
- (2) $(\overline{S_n})^m \sim A(S_n)$;
- (3) $(A^*(S_n))^m \sim A(S_n)$;
- (4) $A^*(S_n) \sim (A(S_n))^m$;
- (5) $(A^*(S))^m \sim A^*(\overline{S_n})$;
- (6) $A^*(S_n) \sim (A^*(\overline{S_n}))^m$.

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